

Correction: Phytophagy of *Nesidiocoris tenuis* triggers the response of *Trichogramma achaeae* to tomato plants infested by *Tuta absoluta*

Pasquale Cascone¹ · Fatemeh Tabebordbar² · Gabriele Cencetti³ · Marco Michelozzi³ · Parviz Shishehbor² · Emilio Guerrieri¹ · Massimo Giorgini¹

Published online: 2 August 2023
© Springer-Verlag GmbH Germany, part of Springer Nature 2023

Correction: Journal of Pest Science

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-023-01647-z>.

The authorship has been published incorrectly in the original publication of the article, due to the error during the HTML creation.

The correct version of the authorship is given below, Pasquale Cascone, Fatemeh Tabebordbar, Gabriele Cencetti, Marco Michelozzi, Parviz Shishehbor, Emilio Guerrieri & Massimo Giorgini

The original article has been corrected.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Publisher's Note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-023-01647-z>.

✉ Emilio Guerrieri
emilio.guerrieri@ipspp.cnr.it

- ¹ Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), National Research Council of Italy, Piazzale Enrico Fermi 1, 80055 Portici, NA, Italy
- ² Department of Plant Protection, Shahid Chamran University of Ahvaz, Ahvaz, Iran
- ³ Institute of Biosciences and Bioresources (IBBR), National Research Council of Italy, Via Madonna del Piano, 10 -Polo Scientifico CNR, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino, FI, Italy